

Heterocyclic Fungicides and Insecticides

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A series of 5-aryl-1,2-dithioles and 5-phenyl-3-hydroxythiophenes have been synthesised and assayed for fungicidal and insecticidal activities against the fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) and the insect *Nephotettix impicticeps*. Majority of these compounds are found to possess appreciable fungicidal and insecticidal activities.

THE findings that dithiocarbamates⁴, 2-thio-Δ⁴-thiazolines⁹ are possible fungicides and the organic sulphones, sulphoxides¹⁰ are useful insecticides prompted us to carry on the synthesis, fungicidal and insecticidal assay of a series of 5-aryl-1, 2-dithiole-3-ones, 5-aryl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thiones and 5-phenyl-3-hydroxythiophenes. A number of new thiophene derivatives have also been prepared. Earlier reports reveal that, the simple 5-methyl and 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-ones and 3-thiones have been synthesised from the methyl and ethyl cinnamic esters by Baumann *et al*¹, Friedlander *et al*² and Thuillier *et al*³, but the yields were found to be 40%. We have applied certain modifications to the available experimental procedures for the synthesis of these dithiole compounds. It is observed that a slightly enhanced temperature range and a longer period of heating has improved the yield of dithioles to 80%. The necessary cinnamic and acrylic esters were prepared from different benzaldehydes and furfuraldehydes¹¹ available. The synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy thiophene starting from 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one by a multistep process has been reported^{1,2}. Yield in the last step was found to be 20%. By changing the alkaline hydrolysis by hydro-

lysis with warm concentrated sulphuric acid, the yield has been improved to 75% for the last step. 2-nitro, 2-nitroso and 2-amino derivatives of the above thiophene have been prepared.

Results and Discussion

The fungicidal activity was determined as per the method of Montgomery and Moore⁶ with slight modification with the fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.). The fungicidal assay was based on the percentage of non-germination at 100, 200, 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations. The spores were kept in contact with the different compounds at various concentrations for 24 hrs.

The study of the fungicidal activity reveals that at 1000 ppm, the percentages of inhibition were of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (80%), 5-(2-chloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (86%), 5-(2,4-dichloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (89%), 5-(beta-styryl)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (68), 5-(alpha)furyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (67%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (82%), 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (80%), 5-phenyl-4-bromo-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (69%), 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (72%), 5(2-chloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (83%), 5(2, 4-dichloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (82%), 5-(beta-styryl)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (61%), 5-(alpha) furyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (61%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (75%), 2, 4-dinitro-

R = C₆H₅, C₆H₄Cl, C₆H₃Cl₂,
C₆H₄-OCH₃, C₆H₄-CH=CH-, C₄H₉O.
(I) = sulphur, (II) = P₂S₅ and Pyridine,
(III & IV) = Methanol, Acetic acid and NH₂NHC₆H₅,
(IV & VII) = Methanol, Acetic acid and
NH₂-NH-C₆H₅(NO₂)₂.
(V) = Bromine and Acetic acid.

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phenyl-hydrazone of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (74%), phenyl hydrazone of 2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (62%), 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitroso thiophene (75%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitroso-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (80%), 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitrothiophene (82%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitro-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (88%), 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-aminothiophene (70%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-amino-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (78%), 5-mono-benzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (80%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-mono-benzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (85%). The compounds, 5(para-methoxy) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione, 5(*p*-methoxy) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one, phenyl hydrazone of 5(*p*-methoxy) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione, 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone of 5(*p*-methoxy phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione, phenyl hydrazone of 5(*p*-methoxy) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one, 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone of 5(*p*-methoxy) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one, 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy thiophene did not exhibit significant activity. The compounds with halogen groups in the 5-phenyl nucleus are the most active. Activities are in the order of 2, 4-dichloro phenyl > 2-chloro phenyl > phenyl. In case of 5-phenyl nucleus having other substituents as *p*-methoxy, beta-styryl, the fungicidal activity is lower than that of 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole compounds. Overall the 3-one compounds (C=O) are more active than the 3-thione compounds (C=S). In case of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy thiophenes with substituents at 2 position on the nucleus the order of activity of its derivatives are $\text{NO}_2 > \text{CH} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 > \text{NO} > \text{NH}_2$. The phenyl hydrazones of all such compounds show good activity. 5-Phenyl-3-hydroxy thiophene does not exhibit significant activity but the phenyl hydrazone of 2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one is active (62%) at 1000 ppm. Out of 31 compounds 10 compounds exhibited good activity. Because at 200 ppm the percentage of inhibition of these 10 compounds were 5(2-chloro)phenyl 1, 2-dithiole-3-one (57%), 5(2-chloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (66%), 5(2, 4-dichloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (73%), 5(2, 4-dichloro)phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thione (64%), 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitroso thiophene (61%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitroso-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (67%), 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitro thiophene (70%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitro-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (74%), 5-mono benzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (68%), phenyl hydrazone of 5-mono-benzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one (70%).

For the insecticidal assay the various insecticides were dissolved in acetone to prepare solutions of 0.0008% and 0.0016% concentrations. The insecticide solutions were sprayed in petridishes. The petridishes were dried. Green rice leaves sprayed with the insecticide solutions were fed into the petridishes. 10 insects, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, were released in each petridish along with a control. The control was sprayed with only acetone. Mortality counts were made after 1, 3 and 6 hrs. The insecticidal assay based on percentage of mortality with time at 0.0016% concentration is recorded in Table 1. This insecticidal assay results show that

2, 4-dichlorophenyl and 2-chlorophenyl groups in the dithiole give fair activity.

TABLE 1—INSECTICIDAL RESULTS CONCENTRATION 0.0016% (% OF MORTALITY WITH TIME)

Sl. No.	Insecticides	No. of test insects	1 hr	3 hrs	6 hrs
1.	5-Phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	0	25	40
2.	5-Phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	10	10	35
3.	5-(2-chloro)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	20	50	65
4.	5(2-chloro)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	20	45	70
5.	5(2,4-dichloro)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	30	60	60
6.	5(2,4-dichloro)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	20	55	70
7.	5(<i>p</i> -methoxy)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	0	25	40
8.	5(<i>p</i> -methoxy)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	0	20	50
9.	5(beta-styryl)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	5	15	30
10.	5(beta-styryl)phenyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	0	20	38
11.	5(alpha)furyl-1,2-dithiole-3-one	10	15	40	40
12.	5(alpha)furyl-1,2-dithiole-3-thione	10	10	30	50
13.	Control	10	0	0	0

Experimental

All melting points were taken in a Toshniwal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected, The IR spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer Infra-Red Spectrophotometer.

A. Synthesis of 5-aryl-1, 2-dithiole-3-ones^{1,2} :

A mixture of ethyl cinnamate (100 g) and sulphur (50 g) were taken in a distilling flask fitted with an air condenser and receiver. The system was placed in an oil bath and heated at 270-80° for a period of 12-14 hrs. The resulting reaction mixture was allowed to cool overnight and repeatedly extracted with hot acetone in which the unreacted sulphur does not dissolve. The whole volume of the acetone extract was filtered, reduced to approximately half the original volume. Dry air was bubbled through the acetone solution when 5(substituted) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one separated as shining brown flakes. Crystallisation from ethanol and acetic acid (1 : 1) yielded fairly colourless product. The yield was 30%.

The physical and analytical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 2. Several attempts were made to condense the meta-nitro; *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxy and 3-methoxy-4-hydroxy cinnamic esters with sulphur employing carbon disulphide, pyridine, alcohol as condensing medium besides, the usual procedure to synthesise the respective 1, 2-dithiole-3-ones, but the attempts failed.

The phenyl hydrazones and 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones of the dithiole-3-ones were prepared following the method of Pasto and Johnson³. Their

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF ARYL-1,2-DITHIOLE-3-ONES

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Sulphur%	
					Found	Calc.
*1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₉ H ₈ S ₂ O	117	64	32.04	32.26
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₄	C ₉ H ₇ S ₂ OCl	103-5	48	28.36	28.15
3.	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₉ H ₆ S ₂ OCl ₂	131-32	40	24.69	24.52
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₀ H ₈ S ₂ O ₂	108	76	29.16	28.98
5.	C ₆ H ₅ OH=CH	C ₁₁ H ₈ S ₂ O	138	82	29.51	29.33
6.	C ₆ H ₄ O	C ₇ H ₄ S ₂ O ₂	161-63	72	35.39	35.22

*Known compound.

infra-red spectroscopic results proved them to be identical with the similar derivatives of the 5-(substituted) phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thiones.

5-Phenyl-4-bromo-1, 2-dithiole-3-one is synthesised by standard procedure⁵.

m.p. 171°. C₉H₇S₂OBr requires; C, 39.56; H, 1.83; S, 23.44; Found: C, 39.51; H, 1.85; S, 23.40%.

B. Synthesis of 5-aryl-1, 2-dithiole-3-thiones¹⁻³ :

A mixture of the required 5-phenyl-1, 2-dithiole-3-one (20 g) and phosphorus pentasulphide (30 g) in pyridine (100 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to 70°. Diluted with 100 ml of distilled water carefully (exothermic reaction). Chilled thoroughly, filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol.

The physical and analytical data are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 5-ARYL-1,2-DITHIOLE-3-THIONES

Sl. No.	R	Mol. formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Sulphur%	
					Found	Calc.
*1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₉ H ₈ S ₃	123-24	80	46.13	46.02
2.	<i>o</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₄	C ₉ H ₇ S ₃ Cl	129	65	39.82	39.66
3.	2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₉ H ₆ S ₃ Cl ₂	148-51	60	34.02	34.20
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₀ H ₈ S ₃ O	118	82	39.14	39.03
5.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	C ₁₁ H ₈ S ₃	201-4	75	45.36	45.15
6.	C ₆ H ₄ O	C ₇ H ₄ S ₃ O	283-86	80	48.23	48.11

*Known compound.

The phenyl hydrazones and 2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazones of the dithiole-3-thiones were prepared by standard procedure⁶. The infra-red spectra studies were made.

In the IR spectra of phenyl hydrazones bands appear at 1020 to 1220 cm⁻¹, 1640 to 1690 cm⁻¹ corresponding -N-H- vibrations and C-N vibrations. Disappearance of band at 1720 to 1740 cm⁻¹ is due to complete conversion of C-O to C. IR spectra of 2, -dinitrophenyl hydrazones show bands at 1500 to 1570 cm⁻¹ due to C-NO₂ (aromatic) and substituted phenyl nucleus. Disappearance of band at 1050 to 1200 cm⁻¹ is due to conversion of C S to C N.

C. Synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy thiophene :

The phenyl acetoxy thiophene^{1,2} (1 g) was dissolved in minimum volume of conc. sulphuric acid on heating over a waterbath maintained at 50-60° for about 2 hrs. It was then allowed to cool overnight and poured into ice-cooled water. Solids (0.75 g) separated out which were filtered, dried, and crystallised from ligroin. Yield 75%, m.p. 78°. C₁₀H₈SO requires; C, 68.10; H, 4.50; S, 18.18; Found: C, 67.90; H, 4.28; S, 18.00%.

Phenyl hydrazone of 2-phenyl-2-thiolen-4-one is synthesised by the standard procedure⁶; m.p. 128°. C₁₈H₁₄SN₂ requires; C, 72.19; H, 5.28; S, 12.00; N, 10.48; Found: C, 72.28; H, 5.32; S, 11.92; N, 10.43%.

Synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitroso thiophene :

This is synthesised by the standard procedure⁷; m.p. 112°. C₁₀H₇SO₂N requires; C, 58.5; H, 3.41; S, 15.61; N, 6.83; Found: C, 58.44; H, 3.45; S, 15.58; N, 6.79%.

Phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitroso-2-phenyl-2-thiolen-4-one is synthesised by the standard procedure⁸; m.p. 90°. C₁₈H₁₃SON₂ requires; C, 65.08; H, 4.41; S, 10.85; N, 14.24; Found: C, 65.12; H, 4.48; S, 10.81; N, 14.28%.

Synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-nitro thiophene :

This is synthesised by the standard procedure¹²; m.p. 101°. C₁₀H₇SO₃N requires; C, 54.30; H, 3.17; S, 14.48; N, 6.33; Found: C, 54.32; H, 3.19; S, 14.42; N, 6.30%.

Phenyl hydrazone of 5-nitro-2-phenyl-2-thiolen-4-one is synthesised by the standard procedure⁹; m.p. 98°. C₁₈H₁₃SO₂N₂ requires; C, 61.74; H, 4.18; S, 10.29; N, 13.50; Found: C, 61.70; H, 4.21; S, 10.25; N, 13.47%.

Synthesis of 5-phenyl-3-hydroxy-2-amino thiophene :

This is synthesised by the standard procedure¹³; m.p. above 300°. C₁₀H₉SON requires; C, 62.83; H, 4.71; S, 16.75; N, 7.33; Found: C, 62.82; H, 4.74; S, 16.71; N, 7.32%.

Phenyl hydrazone of 5-amino-2-phenyl-2-thiolen-4-one is synthesised by the standard procedure⁸; m.p.

152°. $C_{16}H_{15}SN_2$ requires ; C, 68.33 ; H, 5.34 ; S, 11.39 ; N, 14.95 ; Found : C, 68.34 ; H, 5.37 ; S, 11.32 ; N, 14.91 %.

Synthesis of 5-monobenzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one :

This is synthesised by the standard procedure^{14,15} ; m.p. 89°. $C_{17}H_{15}SO$ requires ; C, 77.27 ; H, 4.55 ; S, 12.12 ; Found : C, 77.28 H, 4.58 ; S, 12.10%.

Phenyl hydrazone of 5-mono-benzylidene-2-phenyl-2-thiolene-4-one is synthesised by the standard procedure⁸ ; m.p. 145°. $C_{21}H_{18}SN_2$ requires ; C, 76.36 ; H, 5.45 ; S, 9.70 ; N, 8.48 ; Found : C, 76.35 ; H, 5.48 ; S, 9.67 ; N, 8.44%.

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